

Cuida-AI: Virtual Assistant for Optimizing Oncology Care in Public Hospitals in Recife - Brazil

Interview Script:

Section 1: Interviewee Identification – Demographic Data

- Interviewee's Name
- Position/Role
- Length of Experience

Section 2: Information on the Patient Care Process

- What is your role in the oncology patient care process?
- What is the initial stage of cancer patient care?
- How are patients referred to the institution (e.g., public healthcare system, private insurance, or self-pay)?
- Describe the main stages of oncology patient care from diagnosis to treatment.
- What are the patient care days and hours?
- Are there mandatory steps in the process? If so, what are they and how are they validated?
- Are there situations where the care process changes significantly (e.g., emergencies or urgent cases)?

Section 3: Teams and Software

- Which medical specialties are involved in the oncology patient care process?
- What systems or software are used during patient care?
- Does the process involve multidisciplinary teams? If so, what are the main teams involved (e.g., oncology, radiotherapy, psychology, etc.)?
- How is communication between different departments handled during patient care?
- What types of information are shared between departments (e.g., test results, medical records, professional opinions)?

Section 4: Process Improvements

- Where do you identify the main bottlenecks or delays in the care process?
- Are there communication barriers or lack of integration between departments that hinder the process?
- Do you consider the current process efficient? Please justify.
- What improvements could be implemented in the patient care process?
- Are there redundant steps that could be optimized?